

Selection Criteria: Carpentries Instructor Training Seats — Call 1

Building digital skills training and lesson development capacity in the Netherlands NES domain (DC4NES) Project | 2026

About the DC4NES project

The DC4NES project builds digital skills training capacity in the Netherlands. It is funded by TDCC-NES and runs for two years, starting in December 2025. The project funds 50 Carpentries Instructor Training seats across two calls. Call 1 (October 2026 training) will offer 30-35 seats; Call 2 (February 2027 training) will offer the remaining seats.

Becoming a certified Carpentries Instructor enables you to teach foundational coding and data science workshops at your institution and beyond. The training is conducted in English, and each seat is valued at approximately EUR 900. Certified instructors are expected to teach at least two Carpentries workshops within two years of completing their certification.

Selection criteria Selection criteria have not been developed for Call 1, as oversubscription is not anticipated. Each eligible institution may nominate up to two candidates; given the number of eligible institutions, the maximum number of nominations is estimated at 35 seats. If an institute wants to nominate more than 2 candidates, they can let us know in the application form. This helps us assess demand for the open Call 2, coming in September 2026. Any unused seats will roll over to Call 2.

Related documents

You can find all related documents in the Digital Capacity for NES community on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/dc4nes>

- Eligibility Criteria: Carpentries Instructor Training Seats — Call 1
- Selection Process: Carpentries Instructor Training Seats — Call 1